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INVESTIGATION OF THE EFFECT OF STAR-LIKE POLYMERS ON BASALT FIBRE BIO-COMPOSITES

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Outline

- Motivation and aim
- Research methodology
- Star-like polymer synthesis and characterisation
- Bio-based matrix characterisation
- Composite characterisation
- Comparative study
- Conclusions

Research Motivation

About 6-8% of the world's petroleum production is used in the synthesis of monomers (Bozell, 2008)

Reducing dependability on petroleum based is the first step to a more sustainable future

Poly (n-butyl methacrylate) star-like polymer

Star-like polymer in CFRP composites post-impact displayed high ductility

Smooth, cylindrical surface

Process Methodology

Characterisation of bio-based matrix with star-like polymer

- Differential scanning calorimetry
- Dynamical mechanical analysis
- Tensile testing

Testing of basalt fibre reinforced star-like polymer composites

- Tensile testing
- Low-velocity impact testing
- Interlaminar shear strength testing

Post-fracture characterisation

- Scanning electron microscopy

Overview

MATERIAL	SPECIFICATIONS	~BIO-CONTENT
Basalt fibre (BASALTEX N.V.)	Twill woven 2/2, 220g/m ²	100% igneous basalt rock (43-53% SiO ₂ , 12-16% Al ₂ O ₃ , 6-18% iron oxide, 10-20% alkaline earth metal, and 2-8% alkali)
Epoxy Resin SR GreenPoxy 33 (Sicomini)	Density @20°C -1.159 g/cm ³ Viscosity @25°C - 1780 m.Pas Refractive index @25°C - 1.556	34-36% molecular structure coming from plant origin
Curing Agent LITE 2002 (Cardolite)	Phenalkamine hardener, solvent free AHEW - 104 (g/eq.) Viscosity 25°C - 495 cps	>65% from CNSL (cashew nut shell liquid)
Poly (n-butyl methacrylate) Star-Like Polymer (GTP 490)	Mw – 60467, synthesized by group transfer polymerisation	-

Total bio-based content* ~ 45%

Synthesis & characterisation of poly (n-butyl methacrylate) star-like polymer

- Synthesized by group transfer polymerisation (GTP) using 'arm-first' method.
- Polydispersity of 1.44
- Proven results of ductile behaviour (sticky) within plies of laminates¹

Characterisation of bio-based matrix

- No significant change in Young's modulus was observed
- Stars visually looked more compatible with bio-matrix to conventional matrix

	Maximum Stress (MPa)		Maximum Strain (%)		Young's Modulus (GPa)	
	Bio-Matrix	Conv_Matrix	Bio-Matrix	Conv_Matrix	Bio-Matrix	Conv_Matrix
Pure Epoxy	41.44	43.64	3.4	6.03	2.01	1.09
0.2 wt. %	42.54	66.95	3.4	8.44	2.19	1.23
0.5 wt. %	41.3	65.96	3.2	8.54	2.19	1.28
1.0 wt. %	42.0	71.04	2.9	9.9	2.25	1.45

0.2, 0.5, and 1 wt.% of star-like polymer

Low-velocity impact test

CFRP vs BFRP (conventional matrix) impact energy absorbing capabilities

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Conclusions

- Reducing dependability on petroleum derived materials, is the first big step towards sustainability.
- It is possible to have a high bio-content composite and not have a trade off with low mechanical performance.
- Addition of star-like polymers improves the interfacial adhesion between fibres and matrix, therefore higher load bearing capabilities and excellent impact resistance.
- The novel composite has good energy absorbing abilities making it a possible suitable substitute in the transport industry.
- Future scope of this work is to analyse the effect of a bio content >50% and it's effect on the mechanical performance.

Thank you for your attention

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Q&A